

Mass Immigration and the Effect on Employment and Prices: Evidence from the Ukrainian Refugee Crisis

Samuel Palmer, Maxime Khundadze

Abstract

This paper studies the effects of the large influx of Ukrainian refugees into Europe on employment and the price level of the host country. We investigate the refugee inflow-induced demand- and supply-side forces in an effort to determine their magnitude of impact on employment and inflation. Furthermore, we determine a positive impact of Ukrainian refugees on a country's employment number but a negative effect on CPI. We, therefore, find evidence that negative inflationary pressures resulting from an increase in the supply of workers offset the positive inflationary pressures resulting from increased demand owing to a larger population that would presumably consume more goods.

Introduction

Following Russia's unprecedented February 24th invasion of Ukraine, millions of Ukrainian civilians were forced to flee their country and become refugees across Europe, with the highest concentration being found in neighboring countries. Poland is a country that has received a particularly large number of Ukrainian refugees with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees estimating about a million and a half refugees as of 9/27. This means that Poland, a country of a little under 40 million, has seen its population increase by almost 4% in just a few months. The United Nations has praised the support provided by the Polish and other European governments to Ukrainian refugees in the form of food, housing, medicine, education, etc. At the same time, many of these refugees have found at least temporary work across Europe. In the case of Poland Bloomberg reports 385,000 Ukrainians being actively employed as of August 9th (Skolimowski).

With all of this being said, we have decided to look at how this unprecedented refugee crisis has impacted employment and prices within various European economies. Over the past year, European countries have seen, on average, much greater rates of inflation than the US with CNN reporting that in September 2022, Eurozone countries experienced inflation of 9.9% compared to 7.1% in the US (Horowitz). There are many factors that could influence this relatively higher rate of inflation in Europe. One of which, we believe, could be the continent seeing such a large increase in refugees and, consequently, population over the past year, and we seek to determine if that is indeed a cause of higher inflation, and if so, what the magnitude is. Doing so will require us to disentangle many other complications to European economies also resulting from Russia's invasion of Ukraine such as increased trade restrictions placed on Russia, particularly in the area of imports of petroleum products such as oil and natural gas. What was found from this investigation is a non-statistically significant effect of these refugees

on inflation but a noticeable increase in employment.

In this paper, we will first be examining the existing literature regarding the impact of large-scale immigration on a country's local economy, specifically with respect to employment and inflation rate (our variables of interest). From there, we will be laying out the models that we have developed in order to ascertain this impact on the context of Ukrainian refugees in Europe. We will then briefly discuss from where we have obtained our data, and what it looks like. We will then end with a discussion of our results which show a positive impact of refugees on employment within the host country, and a negative impact on inflation.

Literature Review

So far, the greatest indication that we have about the potential impact of Ukrainian refugees on various European economies comes from a report issued by the OECD in July of this year which uses the demographic makeup of refugees including their age, gender, educational level, to try and project the effect that they will have on host economies. In the report, they discuss the difficulty of projecting the contributions of these refugees to the labor market of neighboring countries both due to a lack of data and the fact that a significant portion of these refugees is between 0-19 years of age. That being said, they projected upwards of a 1.9% increase in the labor force of Poland, though no further projections are made about the potential impact on GDP, CPI, or any other economic indicators (OECD, July 2022). It is also important to bear in mind, this is only regarding Poland which is one of the countries that saw the largest share of refugees arrive and is not the typical case for other European economies. With respect to a concrete analysis of an ongoing immigration flow as it pertains to inflation, Benjamín García and Juan Guerra-Salas from the Central Bank of Chile discuss how the recent surge of migrants

into Chile has affected prices within the country. They begin by stating that absent further information, an immigration shock will result in an ambiguous effect on inflation; there is upward pressure on inflation due to a greater aggregate demand owing to a larger population, but at the same time there would be downward pressure on inflation owing to a larger workforce which should result in downward pressure on wages. Empirically, they find that in Chile, the influx of immigrants did in fact have an upward effect on inflation. This is significant for our work since it would seem to suggest that we would plausibly similarly find a positive effect on inflation, but perhaps one even larger in magnitude than what was observed in this study due to the fact that a much larger portion of the refugees in Poland is composed of children, and therefore less likely to be able to work. Taken with the OECD analysis, we can further see this given the fact that Poland's population increased by nearly 4%, yet projections are that the labor force will increase by less than 2%. As a result, even though countries with larger concentrations of refugees will see greater increases in their workforces, that positive shock may not necessarily offset the upward pressure on prices.

The aggregate effects on inflation discussed above have also been shown to apply to individual markets. For instance, Degen and Fischer 2017 find that in Switzerland, for every 1% increase in the population of an area, the price of a single-family home increases by 2.7% on average. Because most of the population growth in Switzerland is due to immigration, the increase in housing prices within the country can largely be attributed to immigration instead of natural population growth among the native population. While this study is closer to our target countries in a geographic sense given that it is directly examining Europe, it should be noted that the way Ukrainian refugees are achieving housing across Europe is far different from how the immigrants in this Swiss study would be; the Ukrainian refugees are much less likely to rent an

apartment in a traditional sense and would instead be likely to live in government-provided housing, which could influence the effect on the price of housing.

All this being said, the literature is not unanimous in showing the strong correlation between a refugee influx and price increases. Balkan and Tumen 2016 indicate that the unexpected inflow of Syrian refugees in Turkey has actually resulted in the general level of consumer prices declining by 2.5%. The analysis pushes forward an important point regarding the informal labor-intensive sectors in Turkey - which gained a substantial part of the inexpensive Syrian labor supply. Consequently, the authors document that prices in informal sectors have fallen by 4% due to the lower production costs that were driven by the falling wage expenditure. On the other hand, the prices in the formal labor-intensive sectors of Turkey remained unchanged.

The same finding was validated by Aiyar et al. 2016 by documenting that immigrant and native workers operate in completely separate segments of the labor market which translates into the low substitutability between the two. However, contrary to the idea above, one study by Borjas 2006 illustrates a more sizable negative impact that foreign workforce influx can have on wages, prices, and aggregate demand. It would be crucial to consider the informal-formal labor sector dynamics in Europe for Ukrainian refugees. The deputy interior minister in Poland, Pawel Szefernaker, has revealed that a million Ukrainian refugees received the Polish National Identification Number (PESEL) and that 95% of them were women and children. Out of all PESEL holders - a substantial number of 400,000 Ukrainians have taken up legal employment in Poland and thus pay taxes. The remaining 600,000 enjoy access to various public benefits that PESEL provides them with.

The factor of disproportionate representation of women in the Ukrainian refugee pool is of utmost importance to consider when discussing its consequences. As Alden & Hammarstedt 2014 and Ott 2013 discuss - there is significant heterogeneity in labor market performance between different groups. For instance, the Swedish labor market has shown how slow the process of integration can be in the recipient country, especially for female migrants and refugees. These two groups are likely to face considerably worse short-term labor market outcomes. The earnings and employment gaps are particularly pronounced in the first years after arrival. That is to say that we could potentially expect predominantly female Ukrainian refugees who have only been in Poland for 6 months to face the same challenges.

Theoretical Model

The theoretical groundwork to explore the implication of immigration and inflation has been established and extended by Garcia et al., 2020. The intuitive way to determine the connection between these variables, to put it in mild terms, is quite ambiguous and vague in nature. It is due to the fact that, on one hand, the influx of a large number of immigrants creates downward pressure on inflation owing to an increased supply of labor which in turn forces wages/price levels down. However, on the other hand, sudden population growth is fundamentally inflationary since price levels would have to increase owing to an increased demand for goods and services in a given economy. This phenomenon can be demonstrated in Figure 1 – however, for the purposes of presenting the mechanism, the increase in demand completely crowds out the change in wages/price level produced by the increase in the supply of labor. As already mentioned above, the immigration effect on inflation is indefinite since – theoretically speaking, we only know the direction and general pattern of how demand and supply behave after immigration shock. But we are not precisely certain whether the magnitude

of wage/price level hike as the result of the increase in aggregate demand is enough to offset the initial disinflationary supply-side move. Therefore, it is entirely possible that, as shown in Figure 1, an immigration shock could have a negligible impact on wages and/or prices within a country.

Figure 1: Effect of immigration influx on the domestic wage/price level

After the paper by Garcia et al., 2020 examined the relationship between the immigration shock and inflation and wages (two closely related ideas in this context)- the authors found that the magnitude of the initial decrease in the wage/price level is lower than the magnitude of the increase in prices produced by inflationary demand pressure. This implies that immigration shock-induced inflation is present, and it is not only statistically but economically significant as well due to the central bank devising monetary policy to counteract rising price levels resulting from large immigration flows. Since the monetary policy could indeed post-factum respond and address the changes in inflation caused by the immigration shock – it is important to create such a model which controls for the relevant monetary variables' impacts on inflation during the time of immigration shock having its effects on the price level. To put it in other words, to determine

an internally and externally valid relationship between immigration and inflation – we must control for monetary variables. This way we can expand on the existing scarce literature on the macroeconomic impacts of large, nearly instant immigration shocks and essentially provide a more complete model.

Empirical Model

Given that the model above describes two potential avenues of change in a country's rate of inflation: one through the increase in the supply of the labor force having a downward effect on wages and therefore on prices and the other on increasing demand for goods in the country by simply having a greater population, it would make sense to create models of both and compare their effects. Consequently, we have decided to create two models: an OLS model that will show the change in total employment from the previous month as a function of the percentage of a country's population comprised of Ukrainian refugees. The second model that we are going to run is an OLS regression that predicts the change in monthly CPI as a function of the same independent variable in the previous employment model. While neither of these models will be able to tell us the magnitude of the change in price levels caused by either the downward pressure on wages or the upward pressure on demand, they do give us insight on if the theoretical change in employment is in fact occurring, and if the effect of that increase in employment and decreasing wages is overcome by the positive demand shock of the refugees. At its most simple level, these two models are expressed by:

$$\%change\ monthly\ CPI_{ct} = B_0 + B_1 \% \text{ Ukrainian refugees}_{ct} / 2021\ Population_c + \epsilon_{ct}$$

$$\%change\ monthly\ employment\ per\ capita_{ct} = B_0 + B_1 \% \text{ Ukrainian refugees}_{ct} / 2021\ Population_c + \epsilon_{ct}$$

The relatively straightforward first model will give us the percentage point change in a country's inflation rate if the share of its population comprised of Ukrainian refugees increases by one percentage point. The second model differs only in its outcome which instead of being a change in CPI, is now the change in total employment. Given the models discussed in the previous section, we would expect there to be a positive effect of high levels of Ukrainian refugees on employment, and an unclear effect on inflation. Naturally, these models are subject to a significant degree of omitted variable bias and need several controls to account for that. Perhaps the most glaring omitted variable would be the impact of Russia's invasion on oil and natural gas imports into Europe from Russia. Due to a variety of sanctions, most countries have greatly decreased their consumption of Russian petroleum products, so in order to account for this, we will be adding a variable that measures the change in Russian petroleum product exports between a given target month (April 2022 for example) and that same month a year prior (April 2021).

Similarly, Europe (along with much of the rest of the world) has seen significant and lasting disruptions over the past two and a half years owing to the various shutdowns across Chinese cities that have greatly impacted the ability of goods to be both produced and shipped from the country. This supply chain disruption has been a significant factor in rising prices across the world, and so in order to account for it, we intended to create a variable that captures a particular country's share of imports from China as a percentage of their total imports at a given month in 2018-2019 (before the pandemic). From there, we would calculate how much imports have changed from 2019 to the present (2021-2022) and multiply that change by the aforementioned relative level of dependence on Chinese imports. However, monthly data on imports into each European country was not available—it was only yearly—so any impact that

change in Chinese imports would have at the yearly level would simply be fully accounted for in a country's fixed effects given that our period of interest is only over 12 months. We acknowledge the potential effect of changes in Chinese imports, but data limitations prevent us from incorporating them into our model.

As discussed in the previous section, another important control to add is one accounting for the various monetary policies in place throughout Europe in the rest of the world that are being put into effect by various central banks to combat inflation caused by previous years' COVID stimulus packages as well as due to the aforementioned breakdowns in the supply chain caused by periodic COVID outbreaks, especially in China whose shutdowns have caused slowdowns in manufacturing. Most of the countries we will be looking at here are in the Eurozone and thus their monetary policy is determined by the European Central Bank, but with respect to countries like Poland which uses the zloty or the Czech Republic which uses the koruna have central banks of their own which act independently of the ECB while must also be examined in the context of these countries. The way we will be expressing this variable is the interest rate set by these central banks in the time periods observed.

The last main control variable we will be adding is a particular country's balance of trade. For instance, we would expect countries that run a large trade deficit (imports greater than exports) to have higher inflation than those that have a trade surplus. This is expected because traditional economic theory suggests that countries that run trade deficits must supply a greater amount of their currency to the international market than countries that run a trade surplus. This greater supply of currency in turn devalues that currency and causes relative prices to be higher and thus we would observe greater inflation in those countries, all else equal. This is particularly important given the examination of Russia's invasion of Ukraine; the loss of Russia as a trade

partner for both imports and exports has significantly altered the balance of trade of European countries in perhaps different ways for each country and therefore must be accounted for. This balance of trade variable will be indexed to the size of each country's economy so as to not give an outsized impact to larger economies which we would expect to have higher magnitudes of either imports or exports. As a result, our final OLS models look like:

$$\begin{aligned} \%change\ monthly\ CPI_{ct} = & B_0 + (B_1\ Ukrainian\ Refugees_{ct} / 2021\ Population_c) + B_2\ (Change\ in \\ & Russian\ Petroleum\ Imports_{ct}) + B_3\ (Interest\ Rate_{ct}) + B_4\ (Trade\ Balance_{ct} / 2021\ GDP_c) \\ & + \alpha_c + \alpha_t + \epsilon_{ct} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \%change\ monthly\ employment\ per\ capita_{ct} = & B_0 + \log(B_1\ Ukrainian\ Refugees_{ct} / 2021 \\ & Population_c) + B_2\ (Change\ in\ Russian\ Petroleum\ Imports_{ct}) + B_3\ (Interest\ Rate_{ct}) \\ & + B_4\ (Trade\ Balance_{ct} / 2021\ GDP_c) + \alpha_c + \alpha_t + \epsilon_{ct} \end{aligned}$$

As a heterogeneity check for the first model, we will re-run it using the same controls but changing the outcome variable from CPI which accounts for a typical basket of goods within a country to one specific good or service such as housing or food. Doing this heterogeneity check will allow us to more accurately identify whether or not Ukrainian refugees have an impact on price levels across Europe and if any effect on just CPI can truly be used to identify an effect on prices across various individual markets and differentiate between economy-wide versus industry-specific effects.

Data Description

In order to estimate the empirical specifications given by our above equations, we obtain data from a few different sources. First, and most widely utilized is the *Eurostat* database which, for most metrics, provides monthly updates on a variety of statistics for all EU member states and occasionally provides data for non-EU nations such as the United Kingdom, Switzerland,

Turkey, etc. Given that the data were incomplete for these countries we restricted our data set to include only EU member states as well as Norway and Iceland which also happen to have complete data. As a result, we are left with 29 countries of interest. In addition, the time period for these countries in our data set is over a 12-month period from November 2021 to October 2022 (this final month will probably change to November once that data is available at the end of the month). This 12-month period covers a time frame both before and after Russia's invasion of Ukraine and the subsequent exodus of Ukrainians toward Europe. Examining both pre- and post-invasion indicators allows us to look at the continent's trends prior to the invasion and then after in order to better isolate the effect of large-scale Ukrainian immigration on European inflation. This was done so that we are not just capturing pre-invasion trends and attributing them to our primary variable of interest.

The variables obtained from *Eurostat* for the aforementioned countries include imports of Russian oil and petroleum products (which also includes gas)¹, interest rates, the balance of trade of individual countries and our primary variables of interest, CPI and Ukrainian asylum seekers in a given country. Because there is not any data for total employment at a monthly level, we took quarterly employment data, calculated the difference in employment period over period, divided it by three (the number of months in the quarter), and then evenly distributed that total to the months in between. While not wholly accurate, we would assume that if a country experiences an upward trend in employment over a quarter, that trend would be distributed to at least some extent across all months in between. With respect to the monthly CPI variable (which is indexed to 2015=100), we created a new variable to represent the month-over-month change in

¹ Oil and petroleum products is a product aggregate equal to the sum of "crude oil, NGL, refinery feedstocks, additives and oxygenates and other hydrocarbons" and "oil products". The energy quantities are given in fuel specific units e.g., solid and liquid fuels in thousand tonnes, and natural gas in millions of cubic meters.

CPI in order to get a monthly inflation rate for each country. In addition, because accurate monthly data simply does not exist for the number of Ukrainian refugees at the country level, we are using the total number of applicants for asylum as a proxy for that variable. This data seems to match up well with the few country-wide estimates that do exist (see Appendix 1) which is to

say that countries that have a greater number of refugees have larger requests for asylum from

Ukrainians than those that do not, which may be indicative of relative policy similarity among EU countries for asylum seekers, especially for Ukrainians. Using this data, we then created a new variable using the population figures of each country at the end of 2021 (also obtained from *Eurostat*) to find the proportion of a country's population composed of Ukrainian refugees that have applied for asylum. The remaining variables not already mentioned come from a variety of sources such as the World Bank for instance with respect to the population data.

In order to account for potential seasonal variation of inflation where inflation may simply be higher in all years during the months which saw the greatest presence of Ukrainian refugees and thus bias our estimates, Figure 2 presents monthly inflation over our period of interest and then monthly inflation during the prior period. This display illustrates a variation in the trends of the monthly inflation rates in these two periods across the continent which provides evidence that the results observed from the aforementioned data are not simply seasonal fluctuations in which later months, for whatever reason, simply tend to have either higher or lower rates of inflation. While the period we are focusing on shows an almost constant monthly increase of 1% month over month of CPI, the previous year's monthly changes fluctuate, but steadily increase from nearly a 0% change to close to a 1% change by the end of the period.

Figure 2: CPI across Europe of target time period and previous years' time period

At an aggregate level, as shown in Table 1, accounting for the period from March 2022 onward, Ukrainian refugees now comprise about 1% of the total population of the countries sampled here when looking at a mean with a median of about .57% per country, which amounts to a quite significant increase in population over a period of just over half a year. However, as shown in Figure 3, the share of refugees in a country is not distributed evenly throughout the continent. A plurality of countries sees refugees comprising less than .5% of their population while only 10% see refugees make up more than 2.5% of their population. Unsurprisingly, Figure 4 shows that this heavy concentration of refugees as of October 2022 is almost entirely localized in Eastern European countries that either directly border Ukraine or are located nearby

with numbers particularly high in Poland (3.88%), the Baltic states of Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia (2.48%, 2.14% and 4.61% of the population respectively) and Czechia (4.26%).

Figure 3: Distribution of Ukrainian refugees by Frequency

Figure 4: Percentage of a country's total population comprised of refugees

Descriptive Stats	% Ukrainian Refugee Share of Total Population	% Δ in CPI for countries below the average refugee share	% Δ in CPI for countries above the average refugee share
Mean	1.14	0.98	1.25
Std. Error	0.23	1.04	1.02
Minimum	0.18	-1.66	-1.58
Maximum	4.61	4.6	4.15
Observations	348	236	69

Table 1: Summary statistics

In order to try and glean whether or not a trend exists regarding the impact of refugee share on the CPI of a country, we have also examined the mean monthly CPI change for countries with a below-average share of refugees, and countries with an above average share of refugees (also shown in Table 1). Doing so allows to look at the surface level to see if a trend exists absent any controls. The statistics indicate that countries with an above-average share also tended to experience higher changes in CPI than their below-median counterparts. However, one should be wary in interpreting these results as there are significantly more countries, more months and therefore observations that have a below-average share of refugees as a percentage of their population. Therefore, attempting to draw a causal link between these two absent any further regressions could lead one to conclude an effect that does not actually exist.

Results

To begin, we first estimate the treatment effect of the share of a population that is comprised of refugees on the percentage of a country's 2021 population employed. The results are presented in Figure 5. Models 1 and 2 simply regress refugees onto employment rate absent any controls but do include country fixed effects. Models 3 and 4 regress refugees onto employment while controlling for trade balance and interest rate. Models 5 and 6 add in a control representing the change in Russian imports of petroleum products (expressed in 1000s of tonnes). Finally, Models 7 and 8 introduce a similarity index that is interacted with the share of Ukrainian refugees in a country. This similarity index is based off the percent of a country's population with a tertiary education in each country. This percent is then divided by the percentage of Ukrainians with a tertiary education (57.1%). The results are then put into different buckets: 0 if the quotient is less than .3, 1 if it is between .3 and .4, and so on up to .7 as Ukraine has a greater share of its population with a college degree than any other country in our sample. Doing this allows us to see if Ukrainian refugees are better able to integrate to their host country's labor environment if that country's labor demographic more closely reflects Ukraine's. In addition, all even numbered models only include the months from March 2022 to October 2022, which is to say only the period following Russia's invasion of Ukraine and the resulting wave of migrants. Accounting for all of this, Model 6 is our preferred specification.

Model 6 indicates that a one percentage point increase in a country's population will result in a .347% increase in a country's workforce, a result which is significant at the 1% level. This result lines up with what the theory suggests which is that employment within a country will increase following a wave of immigration. However, we should be wary with the interpretation of this model as it is not saying that of every 100 Ukrainian refugees, around 33% will find employment. It is simply saying that this employment is being created somehow,

and it is equally likely that this could be attributed to the refugees themselves finding employment or due to positive demand pressures caused by the refugees in their host countries that creates a greater demand for employment among native workers.

Model 8 provides us slightly more insight into how this employment could be increased while also reflecting much of these same findings. Although the coefficient on our Ukrainian refugee population is negative, this is only for the countries with the lowest share of college graduates in our sample, and if we take the median bucket that most countries in our sample are in (2), the effect of Ukrainian refugees on the workforce is then positive. This model also reflects that a country with more similar labor demographics to those in Ukraine will have an easier time integrating these refugees as part of the workforce, perhaps because these refugees have the skills most suited to these nation's economies. The fact that employment increases as similarity to Ukraine's labor force does suggests that refugees are much better suited to finding work in these countries which will have a greater effect on employment than those that are more dissimilar and where it is more difficult for Ukrainian refugees to adapt to such different labor conditions and potential jobs.

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5	(6) Model 6	(7) Model 7	(8) Model 8
Percentage of Population Ukrainian Refugees	-0.0515 (0.0399)	0.291** * (0.0868)	-0.0250 (0.0367)	0.324*** (0.0822)	-0.0227 (0.0352)	0.325*** (0.0812)	-0.374** * (0.0598)	-0.330* (0.167)
Share of population refugees*Similarity Index							0.195*** (0.0285)	0.281*** (0.0648)
Trade Balance as a percent of GDP			-0.0111 (0.0067)	-0.0111 (0.00793)	0.00024 (0.0081)	-0.00028 (0.0112)	0.00173 (0.00709)	0.00114 (0.00988)
Long-term Interest Rate			-0.0434 (0.0456)	-0.0330 (0.0629)	-0.0751 (0.0529)	-0.0965 (0.0687)	-0.0882* (0.0458)	-0.0779 (0.0610)
Percent Change imports Russian Petroleum Products					-1.88e-0 5** (7.24e-0 6)	-1.60e-05 ** (6.55e-06)	-1.51e-05 ** (6.29e-06)	-1.30e-05** (5.83e-06)
January	0.109** (0.0544)		0.105* * (0.0514)		0.115** (0.0505)		0.116*** (0.0437)	
February	0.217*** (0.0544)		0.214* ** (0.0564)		0.227** * (0.0582)		0.233*** (0.0504)	
March	0.343*** (0.0560)		0.335* ** (0.0655)		0.356** * (0.0705)		0.369*** (0.0610)	
April	0.450*** (0.0590)	0.0242 (0.0477)	0.432* ** (0.0810)	0.00399 (0.0536)	0.485** * (0.0924)	0.0525 (0.0599)	0.488*** (0.0799)	0.0555 (0.0530)
May	0.552*** (0.0611)	0.0813 (0.0537)	0.548* ** (0.0951)	0.0703 (0.0720)	0.583** * (0.108)	0.126 (0.0776)	0.586*** (0.0931)	0.127* (0.0686)
June	0.650*** (0.0624)	0.156** * (0.0574)	0.648* ** (0.111)	0.142 (0.0928)	0.746** * (0.129)	0.261** (0.106)	0.747*** (0.112)	0.257*** (0.0936)
Constant	44.75*** (0.0385)	44.98** * (0.0415)	44.49* ** (0.0599)	44.68*** (0.125)	44.37** * (0.0712)	44.55*** (0.153)	44.39*** (0.0617)	44.58*** (0.136)
Observations	203	116	189	108	172	96	172	96
R-squared	0.542	0.420	0.562	0.442	0.565	0.495	0.676	0.611
Number of countries	29	29	27	27	26	25	26	25

Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 2: The effect of Ukrainian refugees on employment

With respect to the effect of Ukrainian refugees on a country's inflation rate, the result is somewhat unexpected and contrary to what the theory would suggest. The figure shows no statistically significant effect of the presence of Ukrainian refugees on inflation which contrasts with a large amount of the literature that suggests, especially in Europe, of which suggests upward pressure on inflation resulting from high levels of migration. One possibility is that any positive effects of increased aggregate demand on inflation are mitigated by how well Ukrainian refugees have adapted to the labor markets of their host countries which was discussed in the

previous model. Another possibility is that because these refugees were forced to leave their homes suddenly and unexpectedly, they simply were not able to bring large amounts of wealth with them and are unable to make significant purchases in their host countries which is compounded by the fact that the average Ukrainian is already far less wealthy than the average EU resident. This then results in demand-pull inflation being not as high as one would expect, and when coupled with a large increase in the labor pool, average CPI change is actually as the percentage of a country's population made up of refugees increases. Finally, another factor as to why we do not see the increase predicted by theory is that most if not all of these refugees do not intend to spend a significant time within their host country and will return to Ukraine as soon as they believe it is safe to do so or the war has ended, and thus will not make significant purchases while being refugees, thus not putting a large upward pressure on inflation. As a result, perhaps if this war lasts a significant amount of time and it becomes clear that many refugees will have to stay in their host countries, they will make more significant purchases, but in the short term, that has not yet occurred.

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5	(6) Model 6
Percentage of Population Ukrainian Refugees	-0.285* *	-0.844** *	-0.124	-0.204	-0.116	-0.133
January	(0.130) 0.128 (0.240)	(0.275)	(0.142) 0.129 (0.234)	(0.366)	(0.146) 0.0734 (0.246)	(0.390)
February	0.597** (0.240)		0.373 (0.247)		0.181 (0.267)	
March	1.613** *		1.270** *		1.110***	
April	(0.244) 1.247** *	-0.231	(0.273) 0.619*	-0.588**	(0.304) 0.325	-0.784**
May	(0.251) 0.923** *	(0.256) -0.482*	(0.320) 0.157	(0.270) -1.054** *	(0.374) -0.0243	(0.306) -1.081***
June	(0.257) 1.132** *	(0.268) -0.236	(0.362) 0.130	(0.325) -1.056** *	(0.425) -0.217	(0.371) -1.255***
July	(0.260) 0.401	(0.275) -0.939** *	(0.410) -0.602	(0.392) -1.766** *	(0.497) -0.862*	(0.469) -1.904***
August	(0.262) 0.432	(0.282) -0.878** *	(0.396) -0.425	(0.378) -1.590** *	(0.475) -0.649	(0.444) -1.712***
September	(0.265) 0.792** *	(0.289) -0.491	(0.385)	(0.373)	(0.468)	(0.443)
October	(0.270) 0.776** (0.322)	(0.299) -0.397 (0.373)				
Long-term interest rates			(0.0236) 0.394** (0.153)	(0.0308) 0.371 (0.230)	(0.0348) 0.429** (0.185)	(0.0519) 0.368 (0.269)
Percent Change Imports Russian Petroleum Products from Prior Year					8.47e-06	6.35e-06
Constant	0.463** *	2.253***	0.0583	1.530***	(3.53e-05) -0.0165	(3.81e-05) 1.146*
	(0.170)	(0.196)	(0.232)	(0.490)	(0.282)	(0.606)
Observations	305	218	243	162	216	140
R-squared	0.230	0.241	0.310	0.317	0.290	0.294
Number of countries	29	29	27	27	26	25

Table 3: The effect of Ukrainian refugees on CPI

Next, we examined the effect of Ukrainian refugees on the price of housing. For this, we simply ran the same models with the same specifications as our previous models and changed the outcome to be a change in the housing price index versus a broader consumer price index which. In this, we find no statistically significant relationship between the level of refugees in a country and housing prices which is somewhat interesting. One potential explanation is, as

mentioned earlier in the paper, refugees are not procuring housing through traditional means and are instead being provided housing in mass shelters by the governments of the countries that they are in or are instead being hosted by private households. Consequently, the rental market would not be greatly affected by large numbers of refugees since most refugees are simply not looking for apartments or homes to rent or buy.

Last, we examined the effect of refugees on food prices, much the same way we did with housing. What we found here is perhaps the most surprising results yet as the table indicates a downward effect on the prices of food as Ukrainian refugees increase in a country. While the previous result of no statistically significant effect on housing is conceivable due to the fact that refugees are obtaining housing through non-traditional, non-market means, this result is much more shocking. If anything, we would expect an upward effect of refugees on food prices because, even if it being provided by the government, the government still has to pay for the food which should increase its demand and therefore prices. One possible explanation is that international aid of food and supplies is blunting the price increases caused by increased demand. Another possible explanation for the decrease in prices is if Ukrainian refugees are working in large numbers in agriculture in their home countries which increases output and therefore decreases price, but that is purely conjecture and would make for an interesting examination in a future paper.

With these results put together, we are able to show, expectedly, that a large population of Ukrainian refugees does in fact positively impact employment in the host country; it is simply a larger pool of labor from which to draw. Because of this greater competition for employment, which would put downward pressure on wages, inflation is actually lower in countries that received large numbers of refugees. In addition, the expectation of returning to Ukraine is a

factor limiting the current spending of the refugees and thus not applying the upward pressure on prices that we would expect from more traditional immigration flows.

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5	(6) Model 6
Percentage of Population Ukrainian Refugees	-0.0153 (0.0725)	-0.0803 (0.0747)	0.00936 (0.0660)	-0.0683 (0.0761)	0.0172 (0.0691)	-0.0335 (0.0738)
Trade Balance as a Percent of GDP			-0.0595*** (0.0136)	-0.0209** (0.00942)	-0.0572*** (0.0155)	-0.0233** (0.0110)
Long-term interest rates			-0.175* (0.0963)	0.0884 (0.0817)	-0.235* (0.122)	0.0395 (0.0915)
Percent Change imports Russian Petroleum Products from Prior Year					-0.000168 (0.000438)	-0.000703*** (0.000232)
January	-0.0298 (0.0891)		-0.0292 (0.0847)		0.00702 (0.0912)	
February	-0.0440 (0.0891)		-0.00892 (0.0969)		0.0429 (0.110)	
March	-0.00356 (0.0926)		0.0369 (0.120)		0.111 (0.144)	
April	0.0227 (0.0990)	0.0423 (0.0362)	0.0674 (0.157)	-0.0253 (0.0528)	0.162 (0.197)	-0.0478 (0.0576)
May	0.00986 (0.104)	0.0381 (0.0422)	0.185 (0.187)	-0.0415 (0.0790)	0.323 (0.234)	-0.0366 (0.0850)
June	0.593 (0.369)	0.360** (0.138)	0.539 (0.397)	0.139 (0.178)	0.699 (0.451)	0.0840 (0.182)
Constant	1.055*** (0.0637)	1.071*** (0.0332)	0.984*** (0.116)	0.740*** (0.158)	1.099*** (0.148)	0.862*** (0.187)
Observations	168	85	156	79	144	72
R-squared	0.025	0.124	0.172	0.241	0.168	0.420
Number of countries	28	28	26	26	25	24

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 4 : The effect of Ukrainian refugees on housing prices

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5	(6) Model 6
Percentage of Population Ukrainian Refugees	-0.174 (0.136)	-0.240 (0.255)	-0.337** (0.162)	-0.891** (0.399)	-0.343** (0.154)	-1.027*** (0.387)
January	0.923*** (0.270)		0.887*** (0.266)		0.928*** (0.258)	
February	0.988*** (0.270)		0.770*** (0.280)		0.687** (0.281)	
March	0.594** (0.274)		0.561* (0.310)		0.599* (0.320)	
April	1.794*** (0.281)	1.217*** (0.277)	1.688*** (0.364)	1.275*** (0.294)	1.878*** (0.394)	1.593*** (0.304)
May	1.131*** (0.286)	0.562* (0.286)	0.951** (0.412)	0.618* (0.355)	1.180*** (0.447)	0.876** (0.369)
June	0.831*** (0.289)	0.266 (0.292)	0.478 (0.466)	0.191 (0.427)	0.732 (0.523)	0.556 (0.466)
July	0.841*** (0.292)	0.279 (0.298)	0.364 (0.450)	0.104 (0.413)	0.450 (0.500)	0.318 (0.441)
August	0.413 (0.295)	-0.144 (0.303)	0.232 (0.438)	-0.000951 (0.406)	0.293 (0.492)	0.199 (0.440)
September	0.521* (0.297)	-0.0343 (0.309)				
October	1.425*** (0.312)	0.886** (0.341)				
Trade Balance as a percent of GDP			0.0144 (0.0268)	0.0152 (0.0336)	0.0128 (0.0366)	0.0925* (0.0515)
Long-term Interest rates			0.212 (0.174)	0.194 (0.251)	0.153 (0.195)	0.117 (0.267)
Percent Change imports Russian Petroleum					-1.40e-06 (3.72e-05)	-7.60e-06 (3.78e-05)
Constant	0.791*** (0.191)	1.406*** (0.208)	0.685** (0.264)	1.477*** (0.535)	0.759** (0.296)	2.086*** (0.602)
Observations	319	232	243	162	216	140
R-squared	0.187	0.186	0.237	0.273	0.300	0.373
Number of countries	29	29	27	27	26	25

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 5: The effect of Ukrainian refugees on food prices

Conclusion

The Russian invasion of Ukraine has altered global, and especially European economies in more ways than one. Apart from massive disruptions in trade resulting from new sanctions regimes and Russia being removed from the global banking system, the unprecedented flow of refugees into Europe will have a profound impact on each nation's economy. We have illustrated here that these refugees are, at least right now, causing significant increases in the labor force of

their host countries and that doing so is actually decreasing their monthly rates of inflation. However, a primary reason for this is how short the time span has been between now and the invasion and initial departure of Ukraine. If this war drags on well into 2023, and it becomes clear that many refugees will be forced to stay where they are, the actions, especially with respect to consumption, will begin to change. At that point, the expected impact on inflation that most of the literature indicates is the result of an immigration wave. Going forward, an analysis that updates the models developed in this paper with more data as it becomes available will be much more effective in establishing the long-term effects of such a large flow of refugees into Europe; currently we really can only rely on limited data of about six months.

Appendix

Appendix 1: Asylum seekers as a function of refugees

Germany is the only major outlier that lags behind to grant a relatively large absolute number of Ukrainian Refugees the status of asylum protection. On the other hand, Poland, along with most other countries concentrated in the bottom left, is maintaining almost a 1:1 proportion despite the high number of Ukrainian refugees. This can be explained by the aggressive policy by the European governments to almost automatically grant PESEL identification numbers to all refugees. This way Poland officially accounts for the number of refugees before they quickly move into the labor force. Generally, the relationship is quite linear with the exceptions of Germany, Czechia, and Bulgaria which remain outside of the confidence interval. Hence, the monthly data for the number of Ukrainian Refugees receiving Temporary Asylum Protection is a viable substitute for the total number of refugees. When removing these outliers from our models, we found nearly identical results and therefore kept them included in the final models.

Bibliography

- Aiyar, Mr. Shekhar, Ms. Bergljot B. Barkbu, Nicoletta Batini, Mr. Helge Berger, Ms. Enrica Detragiache, Allan Dizioli, Mr. Christian H. Ebeke et al. *The refugee surge in Europe: Economic challenges*. International Monetary Fund, 2016.
- Aldén, Lina, and Mats Hammarstedt. "Integration of immigrants on the Swedish labour market: recent trends and explanations." (2014).
- Aydemir, Abdurrahman, and George J. Borjas. "A comparative analysis of the labor market impact of international migration: Canada, Mexico, and the United States." (2006).
- Balkan, Binnur, and Semih Tumen. "Immigration and prices: quasi-experimental evidence from Syrian refugees in Turkey." *Journal of Population Economics* 29, no. 3 (2016): 657-686.
- Benjamín García & Juan Guerra-Salas, 2020. "On the Response of Inflation and Monetary Policy to an Immigration Shock," Working Papers Central Bank of Chile 872, Central Bank of Chile.
- Degen, Kathrin, and Andreas M. Fischer. "Immigration and Swiss House Prices." *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 153, no. 1, 11 Feb. 2017, pp. 15–36., <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03399433>.
- Degen, Kathrin, and Andreas M. Fischer. "Immigration and Swiss House Prices." *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics*, vol. 153, no. 1, 11 Feb. 2017, pp. 15–36.

Horowitz, Julia. "Inflation Isn't Going Anywhere. Just Look at the Latest Data from Europe | CNN Business." *CNN*, Cable News Network, 31 Oct. 2022.

OECD (2022), *The potential contribution of Ukrainian refugees to the labour force in European host countries*.

Ott, Eleanor. "The labour market integration of resettled refugees." *Evaluation Report 6* (2013).

Skolimowski, Piotr. "Poland's Gain, Ukraine's Loss: A Hot Job Market Welcomes Refugees." *Bloomberg*, 9 Aug. 2022.

"UN Expert Praises Generosity towards Ukrainian Refugees by Poland and Urges Belarus and Poland to End Pushbacks." 28 July 2022.